

Embedded Edge Platform for Off-Highway Mobile Machines

Challenges and solutions:

Off-highway mobile machines are often operated in environments where limited connectivity is available (e.g., mountain slopes, construction sites, forestry, etc.). Having the ability to process data directly on the machine, instead of transferring it to external computing resources like cloud computing environments, enables on-site processing of collected data and providing it directly to the human operator.

The ruggedized edge computing platform for mobile machines is a powerful embedded system capable of interacting with a large selection of data collecting and output devices. The edge platform can be integrated into the mobile machine to perform image processing, communicate with other external resources (when required), and many more opportunities. It supports a versatility of industrially accepted connectors, providing multiple CAN and Ethernet interfaces, seamlessly integrating standard sensors into the system. It additionally supports up to 4 displays effortlessly, increasing visibility and the possibility to provide required information to the human operator in an intuitive manner.

Impact:

Integrating embedded high performance computing systems into off-highway mobile machines enable them to perform many processes directly on the machine, without being dependant on external computing resources.

Reducing the shared data with external entities also increases the safety and security of the overall system. As the data is handled on the machine it cannot be compromised by externals. Bringing additional embedded computing power to mobile machinery is the first step towards making these machines more intelligent. Removing the human operator from these machines, from tedious work and the harsh and dangerous environments these machines are deployed, will be the first step towards autonomous operation. People will then act more as a supervisor to these machines than as an operator.

Figure 1: Embedded Edge Platform Setup - UC1

KEY BENEFITS

Improved performance by handling data directly on the machine

Future-ready software framework supporting software defined automation

Cost-Effective, through integration of multimodal XR technologies in a single computing platform

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